

Risk Management in Financial Technology: A Systematic Literature Review to Support Sustainability and Security of Digital Financial Services

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Abstrak

The rapid growth of the financial technology (FinTech) sector has revolutionized financial services by enhancing convenience, speed, and efficiency. However, this expansion also introduces significant risks, necessitating robust information technology (IT) risk management strategies. This study systematically reviews the existing literature on FinTech risk management, focusing on frameworks, algorithms, policies, and technical aspects that influence risk management practices. By integrating advanced algorithms such as Artificial Intelligence and Deep Forest with established frameworks like ISO 31000:2018 and NIST, the research provides a comprehensive perspective on managing risks in FinTech, bridging gaps not extensively covered in previous studies. A systematic literature review methodology identified and analyzed 17 key studies from an initial pool of 134 documents sourced from databases such as Scopus and Google Scholar. Findings highlight the critical role of advanced technologies and established frameworks in mitigating risks and underscore the need for continuous adaptation to evolving challenges. This research offers valuable insights for financial institutions and policymakers, promoting sustainable and secure digital financial services.

Riwayat Artikel : Diserahkan : 25/12/2024 Direvisi : 21/01/2025 Diterima : 22/02/2025	Keyword : Financial Technology, IT Risk Management, Risk Detection Algorithms
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INTRODUCTION

The advancement of digital technology has brought significant impacts across various aspects of life, including changes in lifestyle as society becomes increasingly connected to information technology. These changes not only affect how people communicate, work, and shop but also how they access financial services. In response to the demands of the times, financial service providers are transforming towards digitalization, introducing innovations known as financial technology (fintech). Fintech has become a relevant solution to meet the needs of modern society, which demands convenience, speed, and efficiency in various financial transactions. These services include a wide range of products, such as online investments, digital wallets, online credit, and instant loans. Furthermore, the growing trend of online shopping has contributed to the increased use of fintech as a practical and secure payment tool. The presence of fintech not only simplifies daily transactions but also opens new opportunities in financial management, making it one of the fastest-growing sectors in the digital era.

However, the increasingly widespread use of financial technology (fintech) also brings consequences in the form of heightened risks for financial service providers. Therefore, the implementation of information technology (IT) risk management is necessary. IT risk management is a method aimed at evaluating and addressing risks related to information technology through a well-considered approach (Samimi, 2020). Some of the main functions of IT risk management include providing guidance to help executives and management save time, costs, and resources through effective tools for managing business risks. Additionally, IT risk management aims to integrate IT risk management with overall enterprise risk management, assist organizational leaders in understanding the company's risk levels and risk tolerance, and provide practical guidelines tailored to the strategic needs of company leadership in various parts of the world (Sanjaya et al., 2020).

Based on the above description, there is an urgent need to conduct an in-depth literature review on various aspects related to IT risk management in the fintech sector. This study aims to explore further how IT risk management can be effectively implemented to address the challenges arising from the rapid development of fintech. By understanding these dynamics, the research is expected to make a significant contribution to the development of frameworks and strategies for better managing IT risks in this sector. The results of this research will not only provide insights into the benefits and challenges faced in implementing IT risk management, but will also identify the key success factors that can serve as a reference for improving the quality and sustainability of fintech. Therefore, this study is expected to serve as a crucial foundation for developing a more comprehensive IT risk management strategy, ultimately enhancing user trust, operational efficiency, and the competitiveness of fintech in the future. The findings from this review are also expected to offer practical guidance to policymakers, technology developers, and industry players in designing more resilient, secure, and adaptive systems in response to the ever-evolving technological landscape.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a methodology specifically designed for information systems research using the PRISMA method (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses), a guideline aimed at improving the quality of systematic review and meta-analysis reporting (Vrabel, 2015). The overall methodology stages are depicted in Figure 1: Research Methodology.

Figure 1 Research Methodology

The methodology consists of five structured main stages. The first stage involves determining the research topic to identify the primary focus of the study, followed by the second stage, which includes establishing a strategy for searching relevant documents to ensure a comprehensive and systematic search for information. The third stage involves the selection of studies, where relevant and high-quality research is chosen for further analysis. Subsequently, the fourth stage focuses on determining the discussion areas to guide the research toward specific aspects for in-depth discussion, and the fifth stage involves analyzing findings, where the results of the selected studies are examined to generate valid and useful conclusions. According to Vrabel (2015), research using the PRISMA method ensures transparent, systematic, and reliable reporting, thereby enhancing the accuracy and quality of the results obtained.

Determining the Research Topic

In this research, the determination of the research topic was carried out through brainstorming to identify the issues to be discussed, along with determining the subject of the study.

Determining the Search Strategy Design

The description of the search strategy designed in this study consists of the database, search keywords, and search criteria.

Database

This research uses an electronic repository called Scopus, which is under the auspices of Elsevier. Additionally, this study also includes Google Scholar to find more documents related to Risk Management in Financial Technology. Titles, abstracts, and index terms are used to conduct the document search.

Search Keywords

The three steps taken in this review search are as follows: Identifying alternative spellings and synonyms for the main terms. Identifying keywords in relevant documents. Using the Boolean operator AND to search for documents containing the combined terms.

The keywords in this review consist of strings such as (“Risk Management”), (“in”), (“Financial Technology”). These keywords are then combined using the Boolean operator “AND.” The search is inputted into scopus.com to access documents based on the title, abstract, content, and keywords available in the database.

Search Criteria

The search criteria used during the search process are as follows:

The publication year of the documents used is from the last 5 years, specifically from 2020 to 2024. The type of document used is articles. The language used in the documents is English.

Study Selection

Initially, 134 documents were identified through the use of search keywords and search criteria from the Scopus repository. During the search process, the identified documents were collected and tabulated in a list using Microsoft Excel. The list contained six columns: 1) Title, 2) Year, 3) Author, 4) Publisher, 5) Research Objective, 6) Finding, 7) What have we learned (Past), 8) What Other Studies are Now Exploring (Present), and 9) What issues are still unsolved (Future). From the total of 134 identified documents, a filtration process was conducted based on the formulated topic, resulting in 17 relevant documents that could be further analyzed in this study. Additionally, this research also used search keywords and search criteria from the Google Scholar repository to expand the search range.

Determining the Discussion Areas

In this study, the discussion areas to be explored were determined. This was done by creating a list of questions. The purpose of the study is to review the progress of the

research topic on Risk Management in Financial Technology. To achieve this goal, four research questions were formulated as follows:

What frameworks can be used for risk management in financial technology?, What algorithms can be used for risk management in financial technology?, What are the legal aspects of risk management in financial technology?, What technical aspects influence risk management in financial technology?

Analysis of Findings

This stage analyzes 17 documents from Scopus and other documents obtained from Google Scholar. The selected documents are then analyzed to address the areas or questions that have been formulated.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of findings is reported based on the formulated research questions.

A. Frameworks that can be used for risk management in Financial Technology (FinTech).

The development of financial technology has led to numerous violations arising from digital payment systems, making it essential to consider risk management to minimize emerging risks. Several risk management frameworks are employed in managing financial technology risks. Banks in Uganda consider that adopting the ISO 31000:2018 framework design, with a particular emphasis on Information Systems/DFS risk management, combined with modifications from the NIST 2018 Risk Management Framework (RMF), can be applied in designing a Risk Management Framework (RMF) for Digital Finance Services (DFS) (Arim & Wamema, 2022). The framework consists of six main components: Leadership and Commitment, Integration, Design, Implementation, Evaluation, and Improvement, designed to support risk management in Information Systems or Digital Finance Services (DFS) within banks. In its implementation, the framework encompasses seven primary steps or subcomponents. These steps include: preparing (Process Initiation), categorizing, selecting (Select), implementing, assessing, authorizing, and monitoring. All these steps are designed to ensure a structured and effective risk management process, from the initial planning phase to continuous monitoring and evaluation, thereby supporting the sustainability and security of digital financial services.

Many banks fail due to the inability to meet ISO 31000 standards, leading to various issues, ranging from governance problems to systems failing to achieve business objectives. This is attributed to the failure of supervisory boards and senior managers in fulfilling their responsibilities and exercising control over the risk management system. ISO facilitates independent audit functions during the monitoring and review phases (Wisnu et al., 2019). In addition to the ISO 31000:2018 framework design, there is also the COSO framework design. Its primary goal is to identify factors that lead to financial statement fraud and provide recommendations to mitigate such occurrences. COSO has developed a common definition for control, as well as internal standards and criteria that companies can use to assess their control systems. This framework is supported by five major accounting and financial institutions in the United States, including the Institute of Management Accountants (IMA), the American Accounting Association (AAA), the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA), the Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA), and Financial Executives International (FEI).

According to COSO, internal control consists of five main components that support one another to create an effective control system. The first component is the Control Environment, which includes the culture, ethical values, and organizational structure that form the foundation of internal control. The second component is Risk Assessment, which involves identifying and analyzing risks that could impact the achievement of organizational objectives. Next, Control Activities encompass policies and procedures

designed to mitigate identified risks. The fourth component, Information and Communication, focuses on providing and exchanging relevant information within the organization. Lastly, Monitoring Activities are conducted continuously to ensure that internal controls remain effective and are improved as necessary. The combination of these five components helps organizations achieve their objectives more efficiently and securely. In the future, research can focus on developing more adaptive and technology-based risk management frameworks to address the evolving challenges in the FinTech sector, such as the use of artificial intelligence and big data in risk prediction and mitigation. Research could also explore better integration between various frameworks like ISO 31000 and COSO to create a more holistic risk management system, as well as strengthening the role of regulation and compliance in managing risks in developing markets.

Algorithms that can be used for risk management in Financial Technology.

An algorithm is a series of logical steps that can help achieve a specific goal. Risk issues in Financial Technology can be addressed, among other ways, by using an appropriate algorithm for risk management within Financial Technology itself. Below is an example of an algorithm that can be used in risk management for Financial Technology.

Artificial Intelligence Algorithm

According Computer Engineering (2022), the technology used in artificial intelligence can simulate and expand human intelligence by making computers behave more like humans and approach human IQ. Therefore, with the help of artificial intelligence, FinTech can quickly identify abnormal fluctuations in financial data and issue alarms in a timely manner, which also provides time to respond to financial risks. The analysis found that when the artificial intelligence recognition system detects abnormal data fluctuations or irregular data, the system will immediately issue an alarm. Before entering the artificial intelligence recognition technology, economic data will undergo transformation analysis. The purpose of the data transformation is to enable artificial intelligence to accurately identify economic data. The use of artificial intelligence algorithms for monitoring and early warning can quickly detect potential risks and then create appropriate countermeasures. Menurut (Fritz-Morgenthal et al., 2022), The European Commission has proposed one of the first laws globally to regulate the use of Artificial Intelligence. The Artificial Intelligence Algorithm is a cross-sectoral Artificial Intelligence regulation that specifically addresses governance requirements around what are called high-risk Artificial Intelligence systems, and more generally recommends the application of principles aimed at creating trustworthy Artificial Intelligence. AIAs in banks prioritizing Artificial Intelligence must be equipped with appropriate risk management, as well as the necessary infrastructure and technology (RiskTech, TrustTech, Algo Audit, Regulatory Sandbox). In fintech, artificial intelligence enhances risk management by detecting abnormal financial data fluctuations, issuing timely alerts, and enabling rapid responses, while regulations like the European Commission's AI law ensure AI systems in banks are governed by trust and risk management frameworks.

Financial Risk Management berbasis SVM Algorithm dan Information Fusion Technology

Support Vector Machine (SVM) is an accurate algorithm that is capable of minimizing the problem of overfitting, and many developers follow quantitative analysis (Sivaram et al., 2020). Information Fusion Technology is a process of combining information from various sources to produce the most specific and comprehensive data about an activity, entity, or event. Information fusion involves combining information

into a new set to reduce redundancy and uncertainty. The SVM algorithm model can effectively classify a company's financial risks and monitor them further. The SVM-based Financial Risk Management (FRM) model can classify financial risks with high accuracy, while the information fusion-based FRM model can further enhance the accuracy of financial risk classification and demonstrate high reliability and effectiveness (Yue et al., 2021). In fintech, SVM algorithms, combined with Information Fusion Technology, enhance the accuracy and reliability of financial risk classification by integrating data from various sources, effectively minimizing overfitting and improving risk monitoring.

Deep Forest

Deep Forest is a tree-based classification algorithm. This algorithm has two core components: multi-granularity scanning and cascade forest structure. In the multi-granularity scanning stage of Deep Forest, the fusion of behavioral information, financial information, and authentication information is realized, and integrated computation is achieved in the cascade forest structure. In FinTech, the Deep Forest model has a good overall predictive effect in credit risk assessment. The addition of behavioral information enables the model not only to ensure the accuracy of predictions but also to effectively improve the ability to distinguish between positive and negative samples, which has good application potential (Yang, 2022). Deep Forest, a tree-based classification algorithm, is particularly effective in fintech applications, such as credit risk assessment, due to its unique structure and capabilities. It consists of two main components: multi-granularity scanning and cascade forest. In the multi-granularity scanning phase, the model integrates diverse data types, including behavioral, financial, and authentication information, allowing for a more comprehensive analysis of an individual's creditworthiness. The cascade forest structure then processes this data through multiple layers, refining the predictions at each stage. In fintech, Deep Forest excels in credit risk prediction by not only enhancing the accuracy of predictions but also improving the model's ability to differentiate between high-risk and low-risk borrowers. This ability to incorporate a variety of data sources and continuously refine its decision-making process makes Deep Forest a powerful tool for managing credit risk and improving financial decision-making.

Fuzzy Neural Network Algorithms

Fuzzy neural network is a hybrid system that combines two methods: fuzzy logic and artificial neural networks. In a study, it was found that a modified fuzzy neural network model can be used for analysis and empirical research on credit risk in financial technology. The fuzzy neural network model is used for processing financial data and assessing risks, effectively solving and improving the risk processing level in the supply chain (Wang, 2021). Fuzzy Neural Network (FNN) algorithms, which combine fuzzy logic and artificial neural networks, offer a robust solution for credit risk analysis in financial technology (fintech). Fuzzy logic allows for handling uncertainty and imprecision in data, such as vague customer behavior or fluctuating market conditions, by using linguistic variables like "high" or "low." Meanwhile, neural networks excel at recognizing complex patterns in large datasets. In the context of fintech, this hybrid system processes financial data, assesses credit risk, and makes more accurate predictions about loan defaults by considering both qualitative and quantitative factors. The use of FNNs also enhances risk management in supply chains, improving financial decision-making by enabling better forecasting of potential disruptions or payment issues, thus fostering more resilient financial systems.

In the future, research can focus on developing more advanced algorithms that combine the strengths of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data analytics for even more accurate and real-time risk prediction in FinTech. Specifically, exploring

hybrid models that integrate multiple algorithms such as SVM, Deep Forest, and Fuzzy Neural Networks could enhance the precision and adaptability of risk management systems.

Legal aspects of risk management in Financial Technology.

The development of information technology has had a significant impact on various aspects of life, including the financial sector. Risk management is an activity carried out to assess, reduce, and monitor risks. Key legal aspects include:

Regulatory Compliance: According to the Minister of Finance Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia (PMK) Number 12/PMK.09/2016, Article 1, Number 3, the risk management process involves the systematic application of policies, procedures, and practices, which include activities such as communication and consultation, setting the context, risk identification, risk analysis, risk evaluation, risk mitigation, as well as monitoring and review. The objectives, benefits, and principles of risk management application as outlined in the regulation are:

Enhancing the likelihood of achieving goals and improving performance.
Promoting proactive management. Providing a strong foundation for decision-making and planning. Improving the effectiveness of resource allocation and organizational efficiency. Enhancing compliance with laws and regulations. Increasing stakeholder trust. Strengthening organizational resilience. Memperkuat ketahanan organisasi. **Data Privacy and Security:** In the financial technology (fintech) industry, data privacy and security are crucial for protecting sensitive information and building customer trust. Threats such as cyberattacks and data breaches require fintech companies to proactively identify and address risks. Strong cybersecurity, including security assessments, encryption, and strict access controls, as well as compliance with applicable regulations, are necessary to maintain data integrity. Additionally, building a strong security culture through employee training and a systematic risk management approach is critical to protecting data and company operations (Karangara & Manta, 2024). According to Negara et al., (2021), Indonesian law, such as UUPK Number 8 of 1999 and PP 71 of 2019, legal protection and certainty are provided for consumers, including the right to be informed and feel safe regarding the use of their personal data. With the increasing use of the internet and smartphones, it is essential for fintech providers to enhance their security systems, including encryption technology, to prevent cyber threats and protect consumer data.

Anti-Money Laundering (AML) and Know Your Customer (KYC) Requirements: A strong national regulatory framework, including financial intelligence units (FIUs) and suspicious activity reporting requirements, is crucial for supporting law enforcement. Technological innovations, such as cryptocurrency, require flexible regulations to ensure effective implementation of anti-money laundering (AML) measures. Regulatory changes in Canada, for example, expand reporting obligations for electronic transactions and virtual currencies. Risk assessment of new technologies and international collaboration are also essential to mitigate money laundering risks and combat financial crime globally (Anichebe, 2020). Igbinenikaro & Adewusi (2024), says that Know Your Customer (KYC) in fintech involves due diligence procedures that include identity verification, risk assessment, and transaction monitoring to ensure compliance with anti-money laundering (AML) regulations. Fintech companies must adhere to regulatory reporting requirements, implement effective transaction monitoring systems, and provide training programs for employees and partners. Additionally, consumer protection through transparency, consumer rights, and personal data protection is crucial, with explicit consent required for the collection of personal data. All these steps are essential to maintaining legal compliance and consumer trust in the fintech ecosystem.

In the future, research related to legal aspects of risk management in the financial technology sector can focus on developing a more flexible and responsive legal framework to address emerging technological innovations, such as blockchain and artificial intelligence, which introduce new challenges in data protection, privacy, and

anti-money laundering efforts. Research should also delve deeper into the implementation of global regulations for cross-border transactions and explore how international collaboration can strengthen the effectiveness of oversight and law enforcement.

Technical aspects that affect risk management in Financial Technology.

With the rapid development of Internet technology, commercial banks have quickly integrated with the Internet, forming Internet finance represented by new products and services such as e-banking, mobile banking, and e-commerce. One of the risks that arises is the risk of default by bank customers based on wireless communication embedded microprocessors in the context of Internet finance. Due to this, a small customer credit evaluation system was designed to test the performance of the bank's credit risk management system (Wangsong, 2022). The customer credit evaluation system has proven to effectively implement risk assessment and early warning systems, as well as promote the sustainable development of banks. Additionally, 5G holds the answer to business needs by bridging cloud and mobility, thereby minimizing the risk of default (Qiu, 2021). The continued advancement of these technologies will be crucial in ensuring that banks can effectively manage and mitigate risks in an increasingly digital financial landscape. In the future, research related to technical aspects of risk management in the financial technology sector can focus on developing more advanced credit evaluation systems using cutting-edge technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and big data analytics to improve the accuracy of credit risk prediction and early detection.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Conclusion

FinTech is the integration of technology with financial services. The presence of financial technology is considered to facilitate financial services due to its speed and practicality. However, the growing use of financial technology also results in increased risks for financial service institutions, thus requiring information technology risk management. This study aims to review the progress of research on Risk Management in Financial Technology based on four areas of discussion: the framework aspects of FinTech risk management, algorithmic aspects influencing FinTech risk management, policy aspects of FinTech risk management, and technical aspects affecting risk management in FinTech.

The risk management frameworks commonly used in FinTech risk management are ISO 31000:2018, NIST 2018, and COSO. The selection of these frameworks depends on the specific needs of the financial service institution's FinTech risk management, as each framework focuses on different aspects.

Algorithms that can be used to support FinTech risk management include Artificial Intelligence Algorithms, Financial Risk Management based on SVM Algorithm and Information Fusion Technology, Deep Forest Algorithm, and Fuzzy Neural Network Algorithm. Each algorithm has its own way of identifying potential risks. The use of artificial intelligence algorithms for monitoring and early warning can quickly detect potential risks and then create appropriate countermeasures. The SVM algorithm model can effectively classify a company's financial risks and monitor them further. The Deep Forest model has a good overall predictive effect in credit risk assessment. The Fuzzy Neural Network model can be used for processing financial data and risk assessment, effectively solving and improving risk processing levels in the supply chain.

Legal aspects also play a crucial role in managing risks, such as compliance with regulations, data privacy protection, and the implementation of Anti-Money Laundering (AML) and Know Your Customer (KYC) policies. Data security and privacy are top priorities, given the increasing cyber threats.

To address the evolving challenges, future research should focus on the development of more advanced algorithms, as well as strengthening flexible legal and

technical frameworks to address new challenges in the FinTech sector, including blockchain technology and artificial intelligence.

Suggestion

Financial institutions need to adopt effective risk management frameworks such as ISO 31000:2018, NIST 2018, and COSO to enhance risk management in the FinTech sector. The implementation of advanced algorithms, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Deep Forest, and Fuzzy Neural Network, will accelerate risk detection and mitigation, especially in credit risk assessment and the processing of complex financial data. Strengthening infrastructure and technology is also crucial to ensure risks can be better managed in the evolving digital environment. Further research is needed to develop more specific regulatory policies regarding risk management in the FinTech sector, as there are no policies specifically governing this area yet. Research should focus on developing policy frameworks that include personal data protection and digital transactions. Additionally, studies on the impact of new technologies, such as 5G networks and wireless communication, will provide deeper insights into the risks arising from technological advancements and the necessary mitigation solutions.

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